

**Facile Synthesis and Microwave Absorption Properties of
Polypyrrole/Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Fe₁₂O₁₉ Composite in the 8-18 GHz region**

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Abstract

The present article reports, synthesis of the Polypyrrole/BSF (PBSF) composite via in-situ polymerization technique and their structural, electrical, magnetic and microwave absorbing properties study in the 8-18 GHz frequency region. The X-ray diffraction patterns reveal the formation of pure hexagonal ferrite phase whereas the Fourier transforms infrared spectrum confirms the formation of polypyrrole/BSF composite structure. The PBSF37 composite shows the highest magnetic moment 59.58 emu/gm rather than the other PBSF composites and pure BSF ferrite also it shows maximum microwave absorption of 89% over the broadband frequency range 8-18 GHz. The maximum shielding effectiveness of 37.49 dB at 15.2 GHz and all other corresponding microwave properties were also studied for the same sample.

Keywords: Composite materials; in-situ polymerization; electromagnetic properties; magnetic moment

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